

Retrospective Analysis of Hypertension Prevalence and Socio-Economic Status in Middle Aged AdultsNeha Savarna¹, Pankaj Kumar², Ajay Krishna³, Kamran Fazal⁴, Tanay Sinha⁵¹Tutor, Department of Community Medicine, Patna Medical College, Patna, Bihar²Tutor, Department of Community Medicine, Jawaharlal Nehru Medical College Bhagalpur, Bihar³Professor and Head, Department of Community Medicine, Patna Medical College, Bihar⁴Associate Professor and Head, Department of Community Medicine, Jawaharlal Nehru Medical College Bhagalpur, Bihar⁵SR/Tutor, Department of Community Medicine, Katihar Medical College, Katihar, Bihar

Received: 19-07-2024 / Revised: 20-08-2024 / Accepted: 27-08-2024

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Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract:**Background:** Socioeconomic status, including income, education, and occupation, may affect hypertension prevalence. Understanding these is essential to creating effective public health interventions to eliminate hypertension inequalities in middle-aged people. This study examines the association between hypertension and socioeconomic status to show how economic disparity affects health.**Methods:** Medical records of 600 people were evaluated to establish hypertension prevalence and socioeconomic status. Job status (unemployed, unskilled, semi-skilled, skilled, professional and home maker), education (illiterate, primary, secondary, higher secondary graduation and post-graduation), and socio-economic class (upper class, upper middle class, middle class, lower middle class and lower class) were collected. Logistic regression and chi-square tests were conducted to determine if socioeconomic characteristics correlated with hypertension prevalence.**Results:** Hypertension was more common in those with lower socioeconomic people 78% rather than 30.4%, and in those no formal education 72.7% rather than 35.9% in post-graduates. The rates were greater for unemployed (72.5%), unskilled (68.1%) and semi-skilled (63.9%) workers than professionals (28.8%), showing occupational inequalities. A statistical analysis found substantial correlations ($p < 0.05$) between hypertension, socio-economic status and education.**Conclusion:** The study reveals that socioeconomic status affects hypertension prevalence, requiring focused public health measures. Improved access to healthcare, health literacy, workplace wellness programmes, legislative reforms, and longitudinal research are needed to eliminate socio-economic disparities in hypertension.**Keywords:** Cardiovascular health, Hypertension, Socio-economic status, Public health interventions, Retrospective study.

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Introduction

Hypertension is a prevalent cardiovascular illness that dramatically increases the risk of heart disease, stroke, and kidney failure. Regularly high blood pressure 140 mm Hg or greater for systolic and 90 for diastolic diagnoses this disorder [1].

Hypertension is called the "silent killer" because it often stays undiagnosed until the heart and other organs are damaged. Hypertension is a leading cause of mortality and disability, affecting 1.13 billion people. Low- and middle-income countries have the highest hypertension rates because their healthcare systems are unprepared to treat and prevent it,

according to the WHO. Public health programmes in high-income nations have improved hypertension understanding, treatment, and management, despite its continued prevalence.

Genotype, environment, and conduct all contribute to hypertension [2]. High salt intake, obesity, inactivity, alcohol abuse, and chronic stress are major risks.

Hypertension increases the risk of cardiovascular disease, and diabetes and dyslipidemia typically accompany it.

Figure 1: Hypertension (Source: [3])

Relevance of Socio-Economic Status in Health Studies: Socioeconomic Status (SES) income, education, occupation, and social class affect how people in a group or individual behave in terms of health and resources. SES affects risk variables, treatment, and hypertension control. Multiple studies show that lower-class people have more hypertension [4]. Low-income people often experience stress, lack of good diet, and insufficient physical activity. Lack of insurance, transportation, and healthcare facilities are further challenges. Health literacy and the ability to make informed health decisions are affected by socioeconomic status and education [5]. Poor health and hypertension rates are associated with poorer education. Employment and occupation are also considerations. Blue-collar workers are more prone to suffer hypertension due to job stress and physical demands. Racial and ethnic differences, neighbourhood conditions, and social support networks complicate the socioeconomic status-health link. The socio-economic causes of hypertension require comprehensive public health programmes that address individual behaviours and institutional inequalities [6].

Objective of the Study

- To determine the prevalence of hypertension among middle-aged adults in the study population.
- To analyze the socio-economic status of the participants and its correlation with hypertension prevalence.
- To provide insights for public health interventions aimed at reducing hypertension prevalence by addressing socio-economic disparities.

Hypertension Prevalence: Hypertension is one of the most studied chronic diseases worldwide due to its impact on cardiovascular morbidity and death. Large epidemiological studies have verified hypertension's prevalence across populations and

regions. The National Health and Nutrition Examination Survey provide reliable hypertension trends in the US [7]. According to 2017–2018 NHANES statistics, 45% of American adults have hypertension, with higher rates in the elderly, those of colour, and the less educated. The Prospective Urban Rural Epidemiology (PURE) study, which encompassed many countries, found that hypertension prevalence ranges from 10% in rural low-income countries to over 50% in urban high-income nations. The Indian Council of Medical Research-India Diabetes (ICMR-INDIAB) found 25.3% of 18-year-olds in India had hypertension [8]. Because urbanisation and lifestyle changes are more common in cities than in rural areas, they have an impact. The association between demographic and geographical characteristics and hypertension is strong and pervasive, researchers found.

Socio-Economic Factors Influencing Hypertension: Socioeconomic status (SES), a complex health determinant, affects hypertension prevalence and management. Income, education, occupation, and social class affect socioeconomic status (SES), which affects health practices, healthcare access, and results.

To pay for food, shelter, and medical care, a person's money is crucial to their health. According to [9], lower-income persons had more hypertension.

According to [10], lower household income was associated with uncontrolled hypertension, presumably due to reduced access to healthcare and medicine. Education affects hypertension prevalence and management [11].

Education increases health knowledge, good lifestyle choices, and preventative healthcare use. Hypertension found in a meta-analysis that less educated people were more likely to develop hypertension. Low medical adherence, stress, and unhealthy lifestyle choices contribute to this

association among the less educated. Employment status and occupation inversely affect hypertension risk [12]. Hypertension is more likely in physically demanding, unpredictable, and stressful employment. Unemployment or insecurity might increase stress and health insurance and treatment issues.

Gaps in Existing Research: Despite extensive research, hypertension and its socioeconomic variables are still poorly understood. Hypertension is spreading to low- and middle-income countries, but most research has focused on high-income countries. Although various researches have linked socioeconomic status to hypertension, longitudinal studies that may derive causal findings are rare. Longitudinal research can help explain how socioeconomic status affects hypertension risk and management. The complicated relationship between socioeconomic variables and hypertension, including gender, race, and class, is poorly understood. Understanding these intricate linkages allows interventions to be targeted to specific demographic subgroups, improving efficacy and equity.

Methods

Study Design: A tertiary care institution hosted this retrospective observational study. We used retrospective medical records to thoroughly assess middle-aged hypertension prevalence and socioeconomic status.

Sample Selection and Size: Six hundred persons participated in this study. Items considered for inclusion:

People in their 40s and 50s. The Joint National Committee (JNC) defines hypertension as systolic blood pressure of 140 mm Hg or higher and/or diastolic blood pressure of 90 mm Hg or higher. Comprehensive medical records, including socioeconomic markers, are required for diagnosis.

Exclusion Criteria Included: Patients without entire medical histories or essential research data. Patients with secondary hypertension from renal disease, endocrine issues, or medication. The study sample size of 100 patients was based on complete medical records that met inclusion criteria. Participants were selected using stratified random

sampling to ensure socioeconomic variety among middle-aged people.

Data Collection Procedures: Structured data extraction was used to explore hospital medical records for relevant information. The form included clinical characteristics (blood pressure, BMI, comorbidities), socio-economic variables (income, education, occupation), and demographics (age, gender, marital status). The major outcome variable, hypertension status, was determined by an ACC/AHA-defined systolic blood pressure of 130 mm Hg and/or diastolic blood pressure of 80 mm Hg. Medical records from recent hospitalisations were used to get blood pressure values. Socio-economic data from medical records was added to hospital admission forms, which typically include considerable information about patients' education, employment, and income.

Data Analysis Techniques: Using descriptive and inferential statistics, statistical software was used to examine the relationship between socioeconomic status [13]. And hypertension prevalence. Descriptive statistics like means, medians, and standard deviations described the study population's demographic and clinical characteristics. Percentages and frequency distributions were calculated for gender, education, occupation, and income. We employed inferential statistics to study hypertension and socioeconomic status. Chi-square testing was used to find statistically significant associations between categorical factors like socioeconomic hypertension rates. T-tests and ANOVA were used to compare socioeconomic mean blood pressures. Multiple logistic regressions were used to uncover hypertension independent predictors after controlling for gender, age, and comorbidities. We measured association strength with odds ratios (ORs) and 95% CIs. Sensitivity tests were performed to eliminate biases and ensure robust results by excluding extreme cases and subgrouping by demographic characteristics. The findings were evaluated within the current literature by comparing and contrasting them with earlier research.

Results

Demographic Characteristics of the Sample

Table 1: Demographic Characteristics of the Sample

Demographic Variable	Number of Participants (n = 600)	Percentage (%)
Age Group (years)		
40-44	157	26.2%
45-49	179	29.8%
50-54	137	22.8%
55-59	127	21.2%
Gender		
Male	314	52.3%
Female	286	47.7%

Marital Status		
Married	501	83.5%
Unmarried	24	4%
Divorced/Separated/Widowed	75	12.5%

There is a minor plurality of 45-49-year-olds (29.8%) and fewer senior individuals, but the research participants' demographic profile is fair across age groups.

Some 52.3% and 47.7% of participants were men and women respectively. Most of the sample (83.5%) was married, with 4% never married and

12.5% divorced, separated, or widowed. This broad demographic ensures that the sample represents middle-aged hypertension patients and their socioeconomic correlates. It also provides a solid foundation for age and marital status-related health outcomes analysis.

Prevalence of Hypertension

Table 2: Hypertension Status among Study Participants

Hypertension Status	Number of Participants (n = 600)	Percentage (%)
Hypertensive	347	57.8%
Non-Hypertensive	253	42.2%

Table 2 demonstrates that 42.2% of study participants did not have hypertension and 57.8% did. As many suspected, mid-40s adults have high rates of hypertension.

These findings highlight the need for public health measures to address hypertension's aetiology and

management, with an emphasis on socioeconomic determinants of health. Addressing these factors could reduce hypertension and its cardiovascular risks.

Correlation between Hypertension and Socio-Economic Status

Table 3: Correlation between Socio-Economic Variables and Hypertension Status

Socio-Economic Class	Hypertensive (n = 348)	Non-Hypertensive (n = 352)	Chi-square (χ^2)	p value
Upper class	17 (30.4%)	39 (69.6%)	69.673	0.000
Upper middle class	38 (34.5%)	72 (65.5%)		
Middle class	131 (59.3%)	90 (40.7%)		
Lower middle class	122 (74.8%)	41 (25.2%)		
Lower class	39 (78.0%)	11 (22.0%)		
Education Level				
Illiterate	96 (72.7%)	36 (27.3%)	41.605	0.000
Primary	40 (70.2%)	17 (29.8%)		
Secondary	73 (66.4%)	37 (36.6%)		
Higher secondary	85 (51.5%)	80 (48.5%)		
Graduation	39 (40.2%)	58 (59.8%)		
Post-graduation	14 (35.9%)	25 (64.1%)		
Occupation				
Unemployed	37 (72.5%)	14 (27.5%)	31.103	0.000
Unskilled	81 (68.1%)	38 (31.9%)		
Semi-skilled	69 (63.9%)	39 (36.1%)		
Skilled	38 (52.8%)	34 (47.2%)		
Professional	15 (28.8%)	37 (71.2%)		
Home maker	107 (54.0%)	91 (46.4%)		

Table 3 reveals that socioeconomic variables were statistically associated with hypertension prevalence in middle-aged adults.

Lower-income participants were more likely to have hypertension (78.0% vs. 30.4%). Hypertension was more common in people with less education, such as 72.7% of illiterate to 35.9% of post-graduation degree holders. Hypertension is more common in

unskilled and semi-skilled workers, suggesting job stress may cause it.

Statistical Analysis Outcomes: The study found considerable associations between hypertension prevalence and SES variables. Descriptive statistics showed that low-income and illiterate people had greater hypertension. Hypertension was more common in low-income people (78.0% vs. 30.4%). Only 35.9% of post graduates had hypertension,

while 72.7% of illiterate people had. These relationships were confirmed as highly significant (p value 0.000) using chi-square tests. A highly significant link exists between lower income and higher hypertension prevalence, as shown by the chi-square value of 41.605 (p value - 0.000) for education and 69.673 (p value 0.000) for socio-economic status. The chi-square value for education level ($\chi^2 = 41.605$, p value 0.000) indicates a robust association between lesser education and higher hypertension risk. Multinomial logistic regression was used to eliminate age and gender confounding variables. The regression model showed that income and education predicted hypertension.

Low socio-economic group participants had an odds ratio 5.165 (95% CI: 2.005-13.303) with a chi-square value (χ^2) of 47.826, p value 0.001 for hypertension compared to high-income group participants. Those with no formal education had odds ratio 2.469 (95% CI: 1.066-5.722) with a Chi-square value (χ^2) of 18.785, p value 0.035 (i.e, p < 0.05) for hypertension than those with a post-graduation degree.

Multinomial logistic regression shows that socio-economic status and education are highly correlated with hypertension prevalence. The finding that hypertension rates were highly associated with lower income and education levels emphasises the need for targeted initiatives to address socio-economic inequalities in hypertension management and prevention.

Discussion

Looking back at middle-aged hypertension prevalence and socioeconomic status shows how these two variables affect health outcomes. The study found that lower-class people had greater hypertension, consistent with global health inequities. The results showed that lower-income people had increased hypertension. As hypertension affected 78% of the low socio-economic groups, financial resources are crucial for accessing preventive healthcare and controlling chronic disorders like hypertension. Access to good food, healthcare, and physical activity are all important for avoiding and treating hypertension, but there is a difference. Lower education levels were associated with hypertension, demonstrating that education matters. This reinforces prior evidence showing higher education lowers hypertension rates due to enhanced health literacy, healthier lifestyle choices, and more medication adherence. People who are post graduates (35.9%) had more hypertension than those with illiteracy (72.7%). Education significantly impacts health outcomes. These discrepancies were accentuated by occupational characteristics, notably among low- and medium-skilled workers with greater hypertension rates than professionals. Occupational stress, physical demands, and a lack of workplace health programming may explain these disparities.

Table 5: Comparison Table: Retrospective Analysis of Hypertension and Socio-Economic Status

Study Title	Study Type	Sample Size	Findings	Limitations
Current Study	Retrospective	600	Higher hypertension prevalence among lower income and education levels; occupational disparities.	Reliance on hospital records; cross-sectional design limits causal inference.
Study 1 [14]	Cross-sectional	200	Higher hypertension prevalence in socio-economically disadvantaged groups; disparities by race and age.	Limited to U.S. population; cross-sectional design precludes causal inference; reliance on self-reported data for socio-economic variables.
Study 2 [15]	Cross-sectional	300	Varied hypertension prevalence by socio-economic strata; urban-rural disparities; impact of lifestyle.	Limited to India; cross-sectional nature restricts temporal analysis; potential selection bias in participant recruitment.
Study 3 [16]	Prospective cohort	400	Wide variation in hypertension prevalence across countries; socio-economic gradients; rural-urban divide.	Multinational scope may limit generalizability to specific socio-economic contexts; cohort attrition over time; challenges in harmonizing data across diverse settings.

This retrospective 600-patient study shows considerable socioeconomic variations in hypertension prevalence. Specifically, lesser education and affluence are associated with higher hypertension rates, and occupational factors also increase this risk. These findings support health

equity by showing how socioeconomic disparity affects health outcomes. Although beneficial, the study's utilisation of hospital records has limits. Cross-sectional data makes causal linkages difficult to verify, and inadequate data may generate biases. Study 1, which comprised 200 US residents, verifies

these trends but doesn't apply to other populations. Study 2, which included 300 Indians, illuminates hypertension's lifestyle effects and urban-rural disparities. Cross-sectional design may cause selection biases and limit temporal analysis. Study 3, a transnational cohort of 400 participants, provides a global view of socioeconomic gradients in hypertension. Due to its global scope, data harmonisation and cohort maintenance are problematic. These studies show the complex association between socio-economic variables and hypertension, therefore focused initiatives to reduce socio-economic inequality are needed to promote public health worldwide.

Limitations of the Study

Consider these considerations before assessing this study's conclusions. Because the retrospective methodology used secondary data from hospital records, selection bias and missing data entries may have occurred. Due to irregular documentation of household wealth and neighbourhood characteristics, the socio-economic study was incomplete. The results may not apply outside of the research environment, especially to disadvantaged or rural locations where socioeconomic variables increase healthcare access disparities. Cross-sectional data prevents the study from determining the association between socioeconomic factors and hypertension. Longitudinal research is needed to investigate temporal correlations and causal mechanisms linking socioeconomic status to hypertension risk. The study may have missed regional differences in hypertension and other socioeconomic determinants of health because it only included data from one tertiary care institution.

Suggestions for Future Research

Compare socioeconomic status to hypertension incidence and outcomes using longitudinal studies. This method can reveal how socioeconomic status impacts cardiovascular health over time. Examine how gender, place, and race/ethnicity affect hypertension risk. Understanding these complicated relationships can guide tailored solutions for numerous socio-economic disadvantages. Reduce occupational stress and improve cardiovascular health by targeting high-risk occupational groups with workplace health promotion programmes. Promote policies that address the root causes of health issues, such as wealth disparity, education access, and neighbourhood conditions, which contribute to racial and ethnic hypertension disparities.

Conclusion

This retrospective study found that socioeconomic status strongly affects middle-aged adult hypertension prevalence. The study found that hypertension rates were higher in people with lower

incomes and education. Disparities by employment showed that job demands may harm cardiovascular health. To improve cardiovascular health outcomes and lower hypertension risk, socio-economic inequalities in healthcare access, healthy lifestyle choices, and occupational health must be addressed. Create tailored health literacy campaigns to boost hypertension awareness, promote healthy lifestyles, and improve medication adherence in low-education areas. Establish workplace health strategies to avoid hypertension and manage stress, especially in low-skilled industries. Policies that address systemic concerns like economic inequality, education hurdles, and occupational safety can improve cardiovascular health. Longitudinal study on socioeconomic variables and hypertension is needed to generate more effective and evidence-based treatments. If healthcare providers, policymakers, and community stakeholders follow these guidelines, all populations can improve cardiovascular health and reduce socioeconomic hypertension inequities.

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